

Comments on WP2200 (Progress Report on the AR, 1983 September 9)

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In a draft report dated 1983-09-09, F van Leeuwen outlines the general strategy for the Attitude Reconstitution (AR). Compared with previous concepts, as described mainly in NDAC/LO/006 (Attitude Reconstitution Using Splines) and NDAC/LO/014 (Definition of AR), the report proposes a number of important modifications. Many of these are significant improvements, while others appear unmotivated or dubious to me. As far as I understand, the main modifications are as follows.

1. Reformulation of splines to ensure strict continuity at knots other than jet firings and to minimize the number of parameters to be estimated.
2. Direct inclusion of gyro readings (as rate observations) instead of integrated quantities (moments).
3. Direct least-squares solution for intervals of several hours (e.g. delimited by Earth occultations) by means of Householder transformations.
4. Inclusion of gyro drifts in the form of scale errors, assumed to be constant in the solution interval, replacing the stochastic (Markov) model.
5. A new set of attitude angles (ξ, θ, w) relating to a nominal position of the sun. These (plus λ_s) would replace the previous angles ($\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega$).
6. Construction of an "ephemeris attitude" (linear in ξ, θ, w) from which a reference attitude is obtained by superposing harmonics. The latter are derived by harmonic analysis of the gyro signals.
7. The AR is split into independent solutions for the z axis pointing (ξ, θ) and the spin angle (w).

Items 1-4 together constitute an important conceptual, mathematical, and algorithmic simplification with respect to earlier ideas. On these points I have only a few remarks:

C1. It may be preferred to work with higher-order splines (than cubic) and possibly reduce the number of knots, in order to get a natural representation of discontinuities in the torque derivatives from shadowing etc. The choice of splines will have to take into account the possible use of dynamical smoothing later in the processing (cf NDAC/LO/025).

C2. The gyro readings should go into the right-hand sides of the observation equations without transformation (projection onto $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$). (Possibly they can be averaged over short time intervals to reduce the number of equations.) The reason for this is to guarantee, as far as possible, uncorrelated observation equations, since we cannot assume that the gyro input axes are orthogonal.

C4. The equivalent to a gyro drift in the integrated (angle) domain is not a scale error, but a constant rate offset (bias). There is a scale error too, of course, but this is in practice either unimportant or can be absorbed by the bias estimate. This is due to the near-constancy of the angular velocity vector in the telescope frame (the angle between $\underline{\omega}$ and $\underline{z}$ is of the order of $10'$ or < 0.01 rad): only the varying part of the vector would require a scale error, in addition to a bias, for correct modelling. Thus, as a first approximation, we must estimate a bias (with coefficient 1 in the observation equations) and not a scale error (with coefficient $\underline{a}'\underline{\omega}$, $\underline{a}$ = gyro input axis). The time scale for variations of the bias may be of the order of 10^5 s, so it is perhaps not sufficient to assume a constant value (per gyro) throughout a 12 h interval, say. The AR should allow low-order polynomial representations of the biases.

Concerning items 5-7, I see no point whatsoever in using other attitude angles than α_z , δ_z , ω , and I do not think the methods described will be satisfactory:

C5. At one point, during our meeting in London on October 3-4, I thought that the new angles (ξ , θ , w) had a distinct advantage over (α_z , δ_z , ω), namely in the definition of $w=0$ at the (nominal) "subsolar" point. I thought that this gave a better separation of the spin angle (w or ω) in

respective system) from the pointing angles $(\xi, \theta$ or $\alpha_z, \delta_z)$. I have since realized that the two representations are exactly equivalent in this respect. I shall elaborate on this below, see point (II).

The arguments for the new representation are, if I understand correctly, roughly the following.

- (i) The angles (ξ, θ, w) , being directly related to the nominal motion of the satellite and to the (nominal) sun, enable a simpler and more natural representation of the true motion.
- (ii) The intersection of the principal great circle (through the two viewing directions) with a meridian through the (nominal) sun is a more natural origin for the spin angle than the oblique intersection with the equator.
- (iii) The observation equations for the AR are simpler when expressed in terms of these angles.
- (iv) The angles (ξ, θ, w) are precisely the coordinates used to express the relativistic effects and will therefore simplify the corresponding equations (in the PRS solution).

I don't think any of these arguments will stand on closer examination:

(I) This would be true if the actual attitude was very close to the nominal motion. In reality, the perturbing torques (mainly solar radiation pressure) are such that the motion of $\underline{z}$, for instance, is strongly non-linear in (ξ, θ) as well as in (α_z, δ_z) . Moreover, the jet actuations at mean intervals of the order of 500 s make the path of $\underline{z}(t)$ very complicated (Fig. 1); clearly the only sensible representation of it is by means of splines with discontinuous first derivatives (at least) at actuation times. I refuse to believe that splines in (ξ, θ) will do better than splines in (α_z, δ_z) .

(II) A "problem" with the $(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega)$ -representation (which in fact is no real problem) is that the origin of the argument (ω) is defined by the generally oblique intersection of the PGC with the equator, and therefore depends on α_z . Recall that ω is the angle, along the PGC, from the equator to $\underline{x}$. Now imagine (Fig. 2) that the telescope frame $(\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z})$ is rotated a small angle around $\underline{x}$, so that $\underline{z}$ is shifted by $(\Delta\alpha_z, \Delta\delta_z)$ from $\underline{z}_1$ to $\underline{z}_2$. The intersection point on the equator is at Right Ascension $\alpha_z + \frac{1}{2}\pi$, and is therefore also shifted by $\Delta\alpha_z$. We find that the new argument of $\underline{x}$ is

$$\omega_2 \simeq \omega_1 - \Delta\alpha_z \sin \delta_z \quad (1)$$

That is, the argument of $\underline{x}$ changes, although the axis itself remains fixed. The effect is clearly related to the circumstance that the equator is not perpendicular to the PGC ($\delta_z \neq 0$ in general). One might think that it could be eliminated with a different choice of origin for the spin angle, defined by the intersection with a perpendicular great circle (meridian), such as the one through the nominal sun (Fig. 3). We find however exactly the same kind of effect with the new representation, viz

$$w_2 \simeq w_1 - \Delta\theta \cos \xi \quad (2)$$

In fact, if we derive the complete transformations from differentials in the attitude angles to the rotation components in the telescope frame, we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{x}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \\ \underline{y}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \\ \underline{z}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta_z \sin \omega & -\cos \omega & 0 \\ \cos \delta_z \cos \omega & \sin \omega & 0 \\ \sin \delta_z & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\alpha_z \\ \Delta\delta_z \\ \Delta\omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

with the old representation, and with the new

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{x}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \\ \underline{y}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \\ \underline{z}'_{\underline{\epsilon}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \omega & \sin \xi \cos \omega & 0 \\ -\cos \omega & -\sin \xi \sin \omega & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \xi & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\xi \\ \Delta\theta \\ \Delta\omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The SM and gyros sense orientation or rate errors with respect to the telescope frame (rather than, say, an inertial or sun-related frame). The two attitude representations are in this respect equally "unnatural".

(III) The observation equations are not simplified by the new angles. The coefficient matrices contain exactly the same number of trigonometric functions, as indicated already by (3) - (4). But the computation of the rotation vector in the telescope frame (needed for the right-hand sides of the gyro equations) is more complex if the nominal sun is moving, since its angular velocity will in general have components along all gyro input axes.

(IV) This argument is irrelevant, since the attitude angles are not input to the PRS solution. The relevant angles are obtained from the set coordinates (abscissa, ordinate) of the sun and the symmetry axis of the metric, which need only to be computed once per set.

C6. The purpose of the reference attitude is to serve as a first approximation for linearization of observation equations. That is, the true attitude is modelled as

$$\underline{a}_{\text{true}}(t) = \underline{a}_{\text{ref}}(t) + \underline{\Delta a}(t) \quad (5)$$

where $\underline{a}$ is a 3-vector of attitude angles. The coefficients of the observation equations and the C in the O-C's (right-hand sides) are computed with $\underline{a}_{\text{ref}}(t)$, and the least-squares system is solved for $\underline{\Delta a}(t)$ (suitably parametrized). The solution is not iterated. This means that the final attitude estimate, $\hat{\underline{a}}(t) = \underline{a}_{\text{ref}}(t) + \hat{\underline{\Delta a}}$, will have linearization errors of the order of $|\underline{\Delta a}|^2$. If these are to be less than 0.1 as, we must require $|\underline{\Delta a}| < 150$ as, while errors below 1 mas will require $|\underline{\Delta a}| < 15$ as.

The requirements on the reference attitude are thus:

- it must be smooth to at least the same degree as required for the final attitude;
- it shall not deviate from the true attitude by more than TBD as.

The proposed determination of a reference attitude as an ephemeris attitude plus harmonics will probably not satisfy the second requirement, due to the rate discontinuities as jet actuations. In other words, the discontinuities must be allowed already in the reference attitude. Fortunately both requirements can be satisfied quite simply by least-squares fitting the chosen (spline) representation directly to the real-time attitude (or the improved attitude determined by ESOC). The latter has a maximum error of 3-5 as, so if the residuals of the fit do not exceed 10 as, we can be sure that the actual error of the fitted attitude is below 15 as.

C7. It is not possible to separate the solution for the spin angle from that of the z axis pointing, because SM transits over the inclined slits give observation equations involving all three angles. If we furthermore assume that the gyro input axes can have any orientation w.r.t. the telescope frame, the same will apply to the gyro observation equations.

FIG. 1. Schematic representation of true and nominal altitude ($z(t)$) for a time interval of approx. 8000 sec. (Derived from Fig. 3.2.4-45 in E22-HIP-03225, 1982.10.04)

$$\omega_2 = \omega_1 - \Delta\theta \cos \xi$$

FIG 3.

$$\omega_2 = \omega_1 - \Delta\alpha_2 \sin \delta_2$$

FIG 2.